

EXTENT OF PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY LEARNING FACILITATORS IN RELATION TO DISTRICT'S COMPLIANCE WITH CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This research sought to explore various aspects of In-service Training for Teachers with CPD units. It focused on the profile of the learning facilitators, problems encountered & the district's compliance with Program Delivery Quality Standards set by the National Educators Academy of the Philippines. Also, the study aimed to provide insights into the training process & suggests improvements for enhancing the overall effectiveness of teacher professional development programs. This study used descriptive & correlational research designs with a tinge of phenomenological qualitative research design. Findings revealed that: (1) The respondents experienced major problems in pre-training & post-trainings while moderate problems were experienced during training; (2) District is mostly compliant in program management; (3) District is fully compliant with learning management; (4) There is no significant relationship between the demographic profiles of the respondents and the extent of problems they encountered; (5) There is no significant relationships between the extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators from pre-training, during-training, post-training and the district's compliance level in terms of program and learning management; (6) There is gap between the existing guidelines provided by NEAP as basis for district compliance and the actual experiences of the learning facilitators. Training Guidelines must include learning facilitators' welfare; and (7) Themes on Possible improvement in terms of In-service training dwell on the need for more: time, resources, trainings, & full-fledge learning facilitators. Lastly, (7) Future

researchers are encouraged to make a parallel study with increased sample size to further verify results.

Keywords: *In-service training, Learning Facilitators, Continuing Professional Development, NEAP, Compliance*

INTRODUCTION

Learning facilitators are one of the most important assets in every district. They serve as leading source of innovations from teaching strategies, techniques, instructional materials, etc. that's why the Department of Education sets a standard that must be followed for every learning facilitator. These include: master's degree holder, trained in specific area of specialization or field, experienced in related tasks/work, etc. But these requirements are not easily attainable by every teacher. That is why there are only very few teachers who qualified to hold sessions with CPD units in every district. This paves the way for the very few learning facilitators to shoulder all the responsibilities in every In-service program for teachers.

Continuing professional development of all teachers is necessary, yet there are very few who are qualified to facilitate in every school and district, leading to problems or difficulties on the part of the very few learning facilitators. In spite of this, there is not much of research about extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators in relation to CPD or continuing professional development. Also, there's not much research about in-service trainings of teachers and continuing professional development particularly on the lens of the learning facilitators. Thus, this research study aimed to add literature and give voice to the learning facilitators.

Related Literature

Being an effective facilitator is a dynamic and complex task that involves guiding discussions, encouraging participation, and maintaining a balanced environment (Hassan, 2024). It takes a lot of hard work and maximum effort to succeed in it. But the good thing is, strategies can be designed to help facilitators create more productive results.

A facilitator is only a facilitator because participants have trusted them to guide the group to achieve its outcomes. Without this level of trust, the facilitator will fail and the group is less likely to make progress. Salib (2024) pointed out the characteristics of a great facilitator. These are as the following: a. Great facilitators are curious, always open to learning; b. *Great facilitators are centered.* Meaning facilitators are focused and end oriented while mindful and very much aware of himself/herself and the rest of the participants; c. Great facilitators are convertible or flexible and willing to readjust based on the need of the participants; d. Best facilitators are not cowardly or never avoid challenging or difficult questions thrown by the participants; e. Facilitators are not complacent or constantly thinking and reflecting ways how to properly deliver sessions

tailor-fitted for the participants; f. Facilitators are not the center of attention or not dominate the room, instead make room for the participants' to be heard. However, learning facilitators often encounter challenges during session. These involved Aligning participants in a diverse group; Handling silence when people don't engage; and managing participation levels. (Velasco, 2024).

Sometimes the awareness that facilitators' awareness as 'the center of attention' may be quite stressful due to feelings of being exposed in front of many people (*The Magic and the Challenges of Facilitation – YSAFE*, n.d.). But facilitators can deal with anxiety and insecurities by: a. Preparing; b. Knowing the audience well; c. Preparing ahead of time for possible challenges; d. Good practice; e. Boosting confidence by updating knowledge on the topic; and f. Putting things into perspective. In addition, delivering a program with more than one facilitator can be beneficial for both the learners and the facilitators. Two facilitators at a time can offer feedback and support (discprofiles.com, 2024).

Related Studies

Continuing Professional Development is undeniably essential for all teachers in the Department of Education. This enhances adaptability to new educational frameworks (Piala, 2024). Thus, every teacher is encouraged to actively engage in In-service trainings and Learning Action Cell sessions. These are organized intentional learning process for teachers at all school levels from pre-school to high school which is commonly facilitated by teacher-educators who are called in-service "learning facilitators".

According to Fransson, et al. (2008) learning facilitators are often called a "multi-headed monster who perform several tasks to support teachers' continuous development of knowledge and skills. The learning facilitators basically are the core of continuing professional development in every schools. According to Psych Educ (2024) from a research article written by Bicaldo (2024), it was highlighted that continuing professional development has big impact on improving pedagogical approaches, content knowledge, and overall teaching performance of educators adding to its necessity. However, continuing professional development is coiled with challenges for every educator due to costly training related professional development initiatives, not to mention expensive graduate/post graduate studies.

According to Morales et al (2023) there is a need to underscore teachers' involvement in graduate/post graduate studies to improve job satisfaction after engaging in professional development activities. It was further emphasized by Morales et al. (2023) that among all the professional development practices participated by teachers such as Focus Group Discussions, Learning Action Cell Sessions, Community Service Involvement, it is involvement in graduate /post-graduate studies which is utilized the least. As a result, there are very few Full-fledge learning facilitators who are qualified to hold and deliver In-service sessions with CPD points. DepEd order no. 44, s. 2023 entitled Interim Guidelines for the Quality Assurance and Monitoring and Evaluation of the National Educators Academy of the Philippines set the standard of qualifications for

resource speakers or learning facilitators for the in-service program. The learning facilitators must be: (1.) Subject matter experts; (2.) Full-fledge Masters' Degree holder in the field of specialization; and (3.) Expert in professional development.

According to Margalef and Robin (2018), The Resource Speakers or Learning Facilitators are the central for the success of professional learning communities. However, learning facilitators' tasks ranged from organizing group work and supporting community building to generating opportunities by stimulating reflection and by providing access to relevant resources and continuous feedback. In other words, these learning facilitators are not free from difficulties with all the instructional roles. There are outnumbering challenges connected with their roles these involved: a. Time limitations or time constraints and the need to avoid the image of experts (Margalef, and Robin, 2018); b. Difficulties with the decisions when to intervene and when to hold back in a learning process (Williams, 2012); c. Resource constraints/ Financial limitations (Piala, 2024); d. Limited guidance how to prepare facilitators (Freeman et al (2010); e. Balancing work-based activities, personal engagement, institutional barriers and fostering community practices (Psych Educ, 2024); f. Professional development availability, cost and design as well as instructional supervision; g. Carrying out multiple roles (Johnston, 2016); h. Inconsistent practice, safety and accountability (Crozier et al, 2020); i. Barrier to technology implementation or technology is not utilized effectively (Kormos, 2021); and j. Teacher resistance (Lewis, 2026).

Yet, there are very few literatures that really focus on giving voice and support for learning facilitators. It would be really nice to focus on interventions or innovative ways to assist the learning facilitators in giving out their best in every In-service training and LAC sessions. Thus, it is the goal of this study to uncover practicable solutions for the common problems and challenges faced by the learning facilitators.

Based on the series of close readings made by the researchers, the following were found as viable interventions and solutions for the challenges or problems encountered by the learning facilitators: (a.) Research-based characteristics of professional development; (b.) Supportive administration and adequate funds for materials (Richardson, 2003); (c.) Collaboration and reflective practices (Psych Educ, 2024); (d.) Encouraging all teachers to involve in graduate/post-graduate studies(Morales et al, 2023); (e.) Training for facilitators' mental resilience and agility (Lago et al, 2019); (f.) Administrators must design more effective continued learning opportunities and focus on how to effectively integrate technology (Kormos, 2021); (g.) Focus on problem based learning; (h.) Creating approaches to enhance facilitator training and optimizing resources (Salinitri et al,); (i.) Time intensive form of professional development (Lewis, 2026); (j.) Facilitators learn to adapt to the needs of community by reflection and continuous feedback (Margalef et al, 2018); (k.) Collaborative learning on group development and dynamics (Williams, 2012); (l.) Encourage collegiality and make use of outside facilitator/staff or developer if necessary (Richardson, 2003); (m.) Leadership and targeted interventions (Piala et al, 2024); (n.) Fostering supportive environment (Bhati et al, 2009); (o.) Peer-learning and structuring the learning (Adriansen and Madsen, 2012); and (p.) Timely and constant training for learning facilitators.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Age
 - 1.3. Distance from home to venue
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.5. Years of Teaching Experience
 - 1.6. Level of Participated Related Trainings
 2. What is the extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators during the conduct of recently concluded In-service Training for Teachers according to the following:
 - 2.1 pre-training
 - 2.2 during training
 - 2.3 post-training?
 3. What is the compliance level of the district's in-service training with the Program Delivery Quality Standards from National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP), during the recently concluded In-service Training for Teachers with CPD units in terms of:
 - 3.1. Program Management
 - 3.2. Learning Management?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of problems encountered by the learning facilitators during the recently concluded In-service Training for Teachers?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of problems encountered by the learning facilitators during the recently concluded In-service Training for Teachers with CPD units in relation to the districts' compliance level with the Program Delivery Quality Standards from National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP)?
 6. What Possible improvement in terms of In-service training to help somehow lighten load of full-fledge learning facilitators in the district?
 7. What viable interventions can be given to the learning facilitators?
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METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive and correlational research designs with a tinge of phenomenological qualitative research design. Descriptive research involves collecting data to provide an accurate portrayal or detailed account of a phenomenon or population without influencing it in any way. It aimed to observe, document and create a thorough profile of the subject under study, often exploring patterns, behaviors or attributes (Cornell, 2024). Correlational research design is use to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It focuses on how variables change in relation to each other (MSEd, 2023).

Phenomenology focuses on understanding the lived experiences of individuals, which would help deeply explore how learning facilitators (teachers or facilitators) experience problems in work and how in-service training could impact the workload. This design would allow to understand the essence of the learning facilitators' experiences

with training and how improvements could affect their professional lives (Ayton, 2023). Data analysis procedure was made using Braun & Clarke's six-phase framework: examining raw data; making initial codes; having repeated coding process; categorizing codes; developing themes and/or sub themes representing data in tables, figures; and lastly creating the final narrative.

This research is conducted in Jimalalud District 2, Jimalalud Negros Oriental within the Division of Negros Oriental. This study focused on the profile of the nine (9) full-fledge learning facilitators, problems they encountered and the district's compliance with Program Delivery Quality Standards set by the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP).

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher made use of the whole population sampling technique for the (9) nine full-fledge learning facilitator respondents. But out of 9 there were only 8 who was able to participate. The respondents were particularly chosen to answer the set of questions in the study. This means that the researcher intentionally chose the respondents for the study to have an informed understanding of the research problem and the phenomenon in the study. This study encompassed three (3) to four (4) months to suffice all research procedures. Permission letters were approved by the gatekeepers and informed consent were furnished and complied appropriately. Lastly, the researcher sought professional advice and technical assistance from more knowledgeable others and research evaluation experts to validate the data gathering tools.

Research Tools

A survey questionnaire was used to gather responses from the respondents. It scored 0.9340 Cronbach Alpha. Which means is a very good result, indicating that the survey has excellent internal consistency and reliability.

Part 1 was about the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, distance from home to venue, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and participated related trainings; Part 2 was on the extent of problems encountered by the respondents in terms of pre-training, during training and post training; Part 3 was on the districts compliance level with the program delivery quality standards from National Educators Academy of the Philippines, based on DepEd order number 44, s. 2023; Lastly, Part 4 was the qualitative part of the study, which prompts answer for the question "What possible improvement in terms of In-service training can help you somehow lighten your load as a full-fledge learning facilitator in the district?". The survey tool was distributed through Google forms to avoid class disruptions of the researcher and the research participants. Additionally, it was made for the sake of the participants who live kilometers away from Jimalalud, Negros Oriental. Some are from Dumaguete City, Manhuyod, and Guihulngan City.

Statistical Treatment of data

The tools that were used in analyzing and interpreting the data are the following: (1.) Percentage. This was used to show how part is related to a whole. It was used in the profile of respondents; (2) Mean. This was used in getting the average extent of problems and compliance level; (3.) Standard deviation. This was used to measure the dispersion of a dataset relative to its mean; (4.) Pearson's correlation coefficient. This was used in identifying the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of problems encountered in pre-during-post training. Also, this was used to identify significant relationship between the extent of problems and the level of compliance; (5.) 5-point Likert Scale to determine the extent of problems encountered; (6.) 5-point Likert Scale to determine compliance level; and (7.) Cronbach Alpha- This measure was used to identify internal consistency or reliability of a set of items in the survey questionnaire.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Sex Profile of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	6	75%
Male	2	25%
Total	8	100%

Table 1.2 Age Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
25-35 years old	6	75
34-45 years old	2	25
Total	8	100

Table 1.3 Distance from home to training venue Profile of Respondents

Distance	Frequency	Percent
1-5 km	4	50
6-15 km	3	37

16-30 km	1	12.50
Total	8	100

Table 1.4 Highest Educational Attainment Profile of Respondents

Level	Frequency	Percent
Master's Degree holder	5	62.50
With Doctorate Degree units	3	37.50
Total	8	100.00

Table 1.5 Years of Teaching Experience Profile of Respondents

No. of years	Frequency	Percent
5-10	5	62.50
11-15	3	37.50
Total	8	100.00

Table 1.6 Level of Participated Related Trainings Profile of Respondents

Level	Frequency	Percent
District	7	62.50 %
Division	1	37.50 %
Total	8	100%

Table 2.1 Pre-training Extent of Problems Encountered by Learning Facilitators

Statement	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Difficulty in preparing for the session content due to inadequate time.	4.25	0.88	Major problem
2. Lack of support in preparation for the session in terms of resources: Load, internet connection, materials, etc.	3.87	1.35	Major problem
3. Insufficient resources or materials for the sessions.	3.50	1.19	Major problem
4. Difficulty balancing facilitation duties with other responsibilities due to busy schedule.	4.37	0.74	Major problem

5. Insufficient access to training or professional development for facilitation skills.	4.62	0.74	Severe Problem
6. Lack of access to necessary resource materials such as books, research, handouts, etc.	4.00	0.75	Major problem
7. Unclear expectations or roles regarding responsibilities as facilitators.	3.62	1.30	Major problem
8. Dealing with own prejudices, anxiety, insecurity and stress as trainer.	3.62	1.18	Major problem
9. Creating a safe, comfortable and inclusive space for the training workshop.	2.87	1.12	Moderate problem
10. Preparing different visual aids, handouts, activities for each group of participants.	3.37	1.40	Moderate problem
11. Ensuring and instilling relevance of the content and various pros & cons of the applications to the participants.	3.37	1.30	Moderate problem
12. Multifaceted roles, functions and tasks as a learning facilitator.	3.50	1.41	Major problem
13. Access to technology, strong fast and reliable internet connection.	3.75	1.16	Major problem
14. Living in a community far away from the training venue. Have to travel everyday causing stress and burnout.	3.25	1.90	Moderate problem
15. Lack time knowing and studying about the needs, expectations etc. of participants.	3.75	1.16	Major problem
16. Setting SMART objectives in alignment to the participants needs and expectations.	3.87	1.35	Major problem
17. Crafting engaging activities that measure learning outcomes and satisfaction of the participants.	3.75	1.03	Major problem

18. Choosing most appropriate methods, tools, and materials for the session.	3.87	1.12	Major problem
19. Limited time to rehearse or run through session, practice delivery, test equipment, gadget of technology.	4.25	0.88	Major problem
20. Looking for varied smart attires for 5-day sessions as learning facilitators.	4.25	1.03	Major problem
Grand	3.78	0.91	Major problem

Table 2.2 During-training Extent of Problems Encountered by Learning Facilitators

Statement	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1.Meeting and achieving the session objectives on schedule.	3.25	1.38	Moderate problem
2. Technical issues with presentation tools or equipment.	3.25	1.03	Moderate problem
3. Difficulty engaging participants during the session due to lack of interest or lack of motivation.	3.62	1.59	Major problem
4. Difficulty managing group dynamics or disruptive behaviors. (Diverse learning needs among participants.)	3.37	1.40	Moderate problem
5. Participants verbatim or surface level examples and outputs.	3.00	1.41	Moderate problem
6. Participants not following instructions or group rules.	2.62	1.18	Moderate problem
7. Challenges with adapting the session to meet diverse learning styles. (How the participants decode, process or understand	3.25	1.28	Moderate problem

concepts from the sessions.)			
8. Difficulty in communicating clearly and effectively with participants using English language.	2.87	1.24	Moderate problem
9. Difficulty maintaining a positive & inclusive tone throughout the session.	3.00	1.51	Moderate problem
10. Unreliable internet connection during session.	3.87	1.12	Major problem
11. Difficulty managing unexpected technical failure with interactive tools (slide decks, online quiz, polls, etc.)	3.12	1.24	Moderate problem
12. Inadequate space and ventilation of the venue or room set-up.	4.50	0.75	Severe problem
13. Lack of sufficient audio-visual support or equipment in the venue.	3.25	1.28	Moderate problem
14. Dealing with participants' resistance (reluctant to engage discussion) to the content process intimidating the session.	3.75	1.16	Major problem
15. Managing personal stress or anxiety while facilitating.	3.62	1.50	Major problem
16. Lack of emotional and professional support from training management team.	2.87	1.12	Moderate problem
17. Inadequate back-up or support for materials and resources.	3.50	1.06	Major problem
18. Lack of alternative plan in place for key facilitators being absent, sick or unavailable.	3.87	0.99	Major problem
19. Meeting and achieving the session objectives on schedule.	2.87	1.24	Moderate problem

20. Technical issues with presentation tools or equipment.	3.37	1.30	Moderate problem
Grand	3.34	0.85	Moderate problem

Table 2.3 Post-training Extent of Problems Encountered by Learning Facilitators

Statement	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Measuring how participant apply learnings from the sessions into application in the actual work setting.	3.62	1.50	Major Problem
2. Ensuring learning continuity.	3.62	1.50	Major Problem
3. Considering external factors that affects success in application of learning.	3.37	1.59	Moderate problem
4. Inadequate time and interest for debriefing after sessions.	3.75	1.16	Major Problem
5. Feeling underappreciated or undervalued of facilitation efforts.	2.75	1.28	Moderate problem
6. Inadequate feedback from the participants after the session.	3.25	1.28	Moderate problem
7. Problems of follow-up or ensuring participants apply learning.	3.75	1.48	Major Problem
8. Stress and burnout from facilitating sessions.	4.00	1.60	Major Problem
Grand	3.51	1.25	Major Problem

Table 3.1 District's Extent of Compliance Level in Terms of Program Management

Statement	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. The program management team and the resource speakers/subject-matter experts reviewed the quality assured program design and learning resource materials prior to implementation.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
2. The details of the planned program implementation (e.g.,	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant

program objectives, date, accommodation, etc.) are officially communicated to concerned offices/units and target participants.			
3. Attendance is confirmed by participants through an online registration form.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
4. Special needs of the participants are noted.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
5. Training Venue is in an accessible, safe, secure, and peaceful location.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
6. Training Venue has facilities for individuals with disabilities or special needs (e.g., ramps, signposts, toilets, reception, parking, elevator, etc.)	3.37	1.40	Partially compliant
7. Training Venue has a sufficient number of clean and accessible toilets and wash rooms.	4.00	0.75	Mostly compliant
8. Residential Accommodation is clean, well-lit, and well-ventilated.	2.87	1.72	Partially compliant
9. Residential Accommodation is spacious for a maximum of three participants in a room with separate beds and at least one toilet and bathroom per room.	2.62	1.99	Partially compliant
10. Session Rooms can only accommodate 30-50 participants.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant
11. Session Rooms are well-lit, well-ventilated, and spacious enough for the participants.	3.87	0.83	Mostly compliant
12. Session Rooms are arranged according to the session objectives and methodologies	4.37	0.74	Mostly compliant
13. Session Rooms provide designated areas for the members of the PMT.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
14. Session Rooms are provided for breakout sessions as indicated in the program design.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant

15. The equipment/tools/supplies are adequate and readily available.	3.75	1.03	Mostly compliant
16. All quality assured learning resource materials (i.e. slide decks, modules, worksheets, audiovisual presentation, etc.) are adequate and readily available.	4.12	0.64	Mostly compliant
17. There is a provision for fast and reliable internet access.	3.00	1.30	Partially complaint
18. An option for soft copies of printed learning resource materials is available.	4.00	1.06	Mostly compliant
19. Adequate session breaks (15-30 minutes mid-morning and mid-afternoon for snacks and stretching, and one hour for lunch) are provided in a timely manner	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
20. To the extent possible, "working breaks" are to be avoided, unless limited session time necessitates these.	4.50	0.53	Fully compliant
21. An adequate number of health personnel and a first aid kit with commonly used medicines are available.	3.87	1.24	Mostly compliant
22. Information on the venue's emergency evacuation plan is disseminated before the start of the activity.	2.87	1.64	Partially compliant
23. The PMT promotes good solid waste management in the venue by adopting the "clean as you go" practice.	4.00	0.92	Mostly compliant
24. Socially-inclusive, gender sensitive, non-discriminatory, and non-stereotypical language is used all the times in the program.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
25. Healthy, nutritious & adequate meals that consider the needs of the participants & PMT members with special dietary requirements are provided.	4.25	0.70	Mostly compliant
26. Zero-tolerance on the commission of sexual harassment, bullying, &	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant

intimidation is observed; incidents are handled by PMT within 24 hours from receipt of the report or information.			
27. Emerging welfare needs of participants, resource speakers/subject matter experts and PMT are immediately addressed.	4.62	1.06	Fully compliant
28. The pre-assessment is done according to the quality assured PD program design.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
29. The PMT consolidates the results of the participants' pre-assessment.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
30. A short opening program which includes national anthem, ecumenical prayer, DepEd Quality Statement, welcome remarks, & introduction of participants is facilitated.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
31. A management learning at the start of the program to prepare learners for the learning process is facilitated. These include leveling of expectations, discussion of program objectives & matrix, & agreeing on session norms.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
32. A daily management of learning to prepare learners for the learning process is facilitated. These include nationalistic songs, ecumenical prayer, attendance check, energizer, recap, & clearing session of the previous learning experience.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
33. Planned activities that are carried out as scheduled unless modifications are necessary due to emerging needs (results of pre-assessment, expectations, etc.)	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
34. Daily attendance checks are done by the PMT.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant

35. The PMT introduces the resource speakers/subject matter experts.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
36. Program proceedings & participants' engagement are monitored & documented using the program documentation template.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
37. Daily debriefing with the PMT & resource speakers/subject-matter experts is carried out and documented.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
38. The evaluation tool for level 1 is administered at the end of the day according to the quality assured PD program design.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
39. post-assessment is done at the end of the program according to the quality assured PD program.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
40. The PMT consolidates the results of the participants' post-assessment.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
41. A short closing program which includes national anthem, ecumenical prayer, insights, giving insights, giving & acceptance of challenge, way forward, & closing remarks is facilitated.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
42. Distribute certificates of appearance, certificates of participation & certificates of completion as may be applicable.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
43. Distribute certificates of recognition to invited resource speakers/ subject-matter experts.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
44. PD Program completion report is prepared & submitted within 30 working days after the actual implementation of the program using the prescribed format.	5.00	0.00	Fully compliant
Grand	4.47	0.28	Mostly compliant

Table 3.2 Extent of Compliance Level in Terms of Learning Management

Statement	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. The session objectives are explained at the beginning of the session.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
2. The resource speakers/subject matter experts used recognized best learning practices such as motivational/mood-setting activities, etc.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
3. Sessions are delivered based on the quality assured PD program design to ensure that session objectives are met, and any planned outputs are produced.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
4. Appropriate and timely adjustments to content, methodology, and schedule are done to address the emerging needs of learners.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
5. Participants are recognized as active learners & sources of learning are engaged in meaningful discussions and activities. Assistance is given to them if necessary.	4.50	0.53	Fully compliant
6. The resource speakers/ - subject matter experts exhibit expertise of the subject matter by delivering accurate content;	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
7. The resource speakers/ - subject matter experts exhibit expertise of the subject matter by having transition topics in a logical manner;	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
8. The resource speakers/ - subject matter experts exhibit expertise of the subject matter by presenting concepts, information & ideas with clarity and congruence to the training/	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant

session objectives and the type of participants.			
9. The resource speakers/ - subject matter experts manage learning time by delivering sessions consistent with the time allotted.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
10. The resource speakers/ - subject matter experts manage learning time by informing participants of the time required for every activity or assessment.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
11. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by encouraging participants to be actively engaged in the session.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
12. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by applying clean and appropriate humor in keeping the session lively.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
13. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by observing gender, equality, disability, and social inclusion (GEDSI) in engaging with the participants.	4.62	0.74	Fully compliant
14. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant

theory by sensing and addressing the needs, potentials, strengths, and weaknesses of the participants that may affect the learning processes.			
15. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by monitoring the energy level of the participants during the sessions.	4.62	0.74	Fully compliant
16. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by making the learning relevant to the participant's experiences by using "real-life" examples and activities.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant
17. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by utilizing a combination of different and engaging methods/ activities appropriately.	4.37	0.74	Fully compliant
18. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert establish rapport with the participants & encourage participation from them with consideration to their diversity and adult learning theory by giving clear instructions in employing various strategies.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
19. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for	4.50	0.53	Fully compliant

understanding of the participants and processes their responses by asking questions that are clear and focused.			
20. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by asking follow-up questions to clarify participants' responses.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant
21. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by paraphrasing questions for clarity.	4.37	0.74	Fully compliant
22. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by asking higher-order thinking skills questions to elicit participants' ideas.	4.37	0.74	Mostly compliant
23. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by responding in a fair and timely manner with respect to the participants' questions and answers.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
24. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by listening to the participants' ideas or responses.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
25. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by paraphrasing participants' ideas or responses to confirm what has been said.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant

26. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert check for understanding of the participants and processes their responses by conducting formative assessments to check the understanding of the participants.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
27. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert established and maintain a positive/non-threatening and comfortable learning environment.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
28. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by using clear and appropriate language for learners.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant
29. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by expressing ideas with clarity, logic, and correct grammar.	4.37	0.74	Mostly compliant
30. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by using non-verbal communication to reinforce verbal message.	4.50	0.75	Fully compliant
31. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by using well-modulated voice in facilitating the session.	4.37	0.74	Mostly compliant
32. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert use appropriate technology with ease and confidence.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant

33. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert synthesize the responses of the participants and the activities of the session by guiding the group to a consensus or conclusion.	4.62	0.74	Fully compliant
34. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert synthesize the responses of the participants and the activities of the session by highlighting important results of the activity.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
35. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert synthesize the responses of the participants and the activities of the session by generating ideas and concepts from the sharing of participants during the learning session/s.	4.62	0.51	Fully compliant
36. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert synthesize the responses of the participants and the activities of the session by identifying the relationships between activities.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
37. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert exhibits flexibility and adaptability in the delivery of the session to ensure an appropriate response to unforeseen situations.	4.62	0.74	Fully compliant
38. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert presents him/herself in a professional manner by accepting feedback without being defensive and offensive reflects on the feedback for self-improvement.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant
39. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert presents him/herself in a professional manner by always observing proper decorum, warm and respectful behavior.	4.75	0.46	Fully compliant

40. The resource speakers/ - subject matter expert presents him/herself in a professional manner by relating to others with sensitivity and a caring attitude.	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
41. A session that helps participants to synthesize their learning should be facilitated (for learning manager).	4.87	0.35	Fully compliant
42. Learners are prepared for learning applications and re-entry to the workplace through mechanisms like the Workplace Application Plan (WAP) (for Learning Manager).	4.62	0.74	Fully compliant
Grand	4.63	0.47	Fully compliant

Table 4 Correlation between profile of respondents and extent of problems encountered

Variables Correlated	r_s	Verbal Interpretation	$p - value$	Decision
Sex and Pre-training extent of problems	-0.66	Strong Negative	0.25	Fail to reject Ho
Sex and During-training extent of problems	-0.46	Moderate Negative	0.98	Fail to reject Ho
Sex and Post-training extent of problems	0.10	Weak Positive	0.54	Fail to reject Ho
Age and Pre-training extent of problems	0.04	Very Weak Positive	0.92	Fail to reject Ho
Age and During-training extent of problems	-0.66	Strong Negative	0.07	Fail to reject Ho
Age and Post-training extent of problems	-0.46	Moderate Negative	0.24	Fail to reject Ho
Distance from home to venue and Pre-training extent of problems	0.10	Weak Positive	0.79	Fail to reject Ho

Distance from home to venue and During-training extent of problems	0.07	Very Weak Positive	0.86	Fail to reject Ho
Distance from home to venue and post-training extent of problems	0.35	Weak Positive	0.39	Fail to reject Ho
Highest Educational attainment and Pre-training extent of problems	-0.04	Moderate Negative	0.90	Fail to reject Ho
Highest Educational attainment and During-training extent of problems	0.07	Very Weak Positive	0.86	Fail to reject Ho
Highest Educational attainment and Post-training extent of problems	0.29	Weak Positive	0.48	Fail to reject Ho
Years of teaching experience and Pre-training extent of problems	0.23	Weak Positive	0.56	Fail to reject Ho
Years of teaching experience and During-training extent of problems	-0.52	Moderate Negative	0.18	Fail to reject Ho
Years of teaching experience and post-training extent of problems	-0.25	Weak Negative	0.58	Fail to reject Ho Reject Ho

Level of participated trainings and Pre-training extent of problems	0.29	Weak Positive	0.48	Fail to reject Ho
Level of participated trainings and During-training extent of problems	0.09	Very Weak Positive	0.81	Fail to reject Ho
Level of participated trainings and Post-training extent of problems	0.23	Weak Positive	0.57	Fail to reject Ho
<p><i>Legend: Coefficient of correlation</i> $\pm (0.80 - 1.00)$ Very Strong Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.06 - 0.79)$ Strong Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.4 - 0.59)$ Moderate Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.20 - 0.39)$ Weak Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.00 - 0.19)$ Very Weak Positive/Negative.</p>				

Table 5 Correlation between learning facilitators' extent of problems and district's compliance level.

Variables Correlated	r_s	Verbal Interpretation	p -value	Decision
Extent of problems in pre-training and compliance level of program management	-0.44	Moderate Negative	0.26	Fail to reject Ho
Extent of problems during-training and compliance level of program management	-0.60	Strong Negative	0.11	Fail to reject Ho
Extent of problems in post-training and compliance level of program management	-0.68	Strong Negative	0.06	Fail to reject Ho
Extent of problems in pre-training and compliance level of learning management	-0.15	Weak Negative	0.71	Fail to reject Ho
Extent of problems during-training and compliance level of learning management	-0.15	Weak Negative	0.71	Fail to reject Ho
Extent of problems in post-training and compliance level of learning management	-0.49	Moderate Negative	0.21	Fail to reject Ho

Legend: Coefficient of correlation
 $\pm (0.80 - 1.00)$ Very Strong Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.06 - 0.79)$ Strong Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.4 - 0.59)$ Moderate Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.20 - 0.39)$ Weak Positive/Negative, $\pm (0.00 - 0.19)$ Very Weak Positive/Negative.

Table 6 Answers extracted from the essay question in the survey form.

Question: What Possible improvement in terms of In-service training can help you somehow lighten your load as a full-fledge learning facilitator in the district?		
Significant Response	N-vivo Coding	Descriptive Coding
LF-1 none ¹	NONE ¹	NOTHING ¹
LF-2 none ¹	NONE ¹	NOTHING ¹
LF-3 Have a partner ¹ to lighten ² the task.	HAVE A PARTNER ¹ LIGHTEN ² TASK	PARTNER ¹
LF-4 All ¹ things are included in the ² form.	ALL ¹ IN THE ² FORM	ALL ¹ IN ² FORM
LF-5 If the topic is ¹ given weeks before the deadline so that there is ² ample time to make the PPT and study, etc.	TOPIC ¹ GIVEN WEEKS BEFORE DEADLINE ² AMPLE TIME TO STUDY	¹ LONGER PREPARATION ² AMPLE TIME
LF-6 As an introvert, stepping out of my comfort zone and facing people in public is really challenging for me. I do ¹ hope that by next school year, there will be more full- fledged educators, providing additional learning facilitators. I truly enjoy taking time to rest, and I miss being a participant in in-service training sessions. I am not ready being a facilitator but ako ra jd gi face and	I DO ¹ HOPE THAT BY NEXT SCHOOL YEAR, THERE WILL BE MORE FULL- FLEDGED EDUCATORS...	¹ HOPEFUL FOR INCREASED NUMBER OF FULL-FLEDGE LEARNING FACILITATORS.

<p>responsibility. If only acceptable language "NO"... Anyhow, there's still so much for me to learn as a facilitator, and I really ²wish we had opportunities to attend public speaking trainings and participate in simulations to ³improve our skills.</p>	<p>²WISH WE HAD OPPORTUNITIES TO ATTEND PUBLIC SPEAKING TRAININGS</p> <p>PARTICIPATE IN SIMULATIONS TO ³IMPROVE OUR SKILLS.</p>	<p>²WISHING FOR TRAININGS TO ³IMPROVE SKILLS.</p>
<p>LF-7 Requiring us the full-fledge masters in an institution to be the facilitators may be the reason why some of the teachers will not continue their studies in master's degree. Because they think that if they become one of the full-fledged master they will also become a ¹learning facilitator in InSeT which is an additional burden as a teacher. This will cause to stagnation of educational development and opportunities of most of the teachers.</p> <p>Why not ²use the Master Teachers of the department who are honed by experience and very capable in facilitating INSET.</p>	<p>¹LEARNING FACILITATOR IN INSET IS AN ADDITIONAL BURDEN AS A TEACHER.</p> <p>WHY NOT ²USE THE MASTER TEACHERS OF THE DEPARTMENT WHO ARE HONED BY EXPERIENCE AND VERY CAPABLE IN FACILITATING INSET.</p>	<p>¹LEARNING FACILITATOR ADDITIONAL BURDEN AS TEACHER</p> <p>²USE THE MASTER TEACHERS</p>

<p>LF-8 It would be nice to have an ¹assistant or F2. Also, I hope there will be ²more full-fledge learning facilitators in the district so the sessions will be lighter. Also, ³resources for internet connection/load, cartolina, manila, paper, scissors, pens, etc. should be ready in all the 3 parts of the training from pre, during and post. I ⁴hope next time we Lf's will be trained and capacitated enough on our assigned topics. Lastly, I hope they will give us ⁵enough time to prepare for our sessions.</p>	<p>IT WOULD BE NICE TO HAVE AN ¹ASSISTANT OR F2.</p> <p>I HOPE THERE WILL BE ²MORE FULL-FLEDGE LEARNING FACILITATORS IN THE DISTRICT...</p> <p>³RESOURCES FOR INTERNET CONNECTION/LOAD, CARTOLINA, MANILA, PAPER, SCISSORS, PENS, ETC. SHOULD BE READY IN ALL THE 3 PARTS OF THE TRAINING...</p> <p>⁴HOPE NEXT TIME WE LF'S WILL BE TRAINED AND CAPACITATED ENOUGH ON OUR ASSIGNED TOPICS.</p> <p>I HOPE THEY WILL GIVE US ⁵ENOUGH TIME TO PREPARE FOR OUR SESSIONS.</p>	<p>¹ASSISTANT OR F2.</p> <p>²MORE FULL-FLEDGE LEARNING FACILITATORS</p> <p>³RESOURCES</p> <p>⁴TRAININGS OR CAPACITY BUILDING</p> <p>⁵ENOUGH TIME TO PREPARE</p>
<p>LF-9 Unresponsive</p>		

DISCUSSION

Shown in the table 1.1.is the respondents' profile in terms of sex. Data show that majority of the respondents are female (75%) and 25% are males. Table 1.2 is the profile of respondents in terms of age. It shows that majority of the respondents are 25-35 years old (75%) while 34-45 years old takes only 25% of the population.

Table 1.3 presents the profile of respondents in terms of distance from home to venue. It shows that majority or half (50%) of the respondents travels from 1-5km to reach the venue. This further followed by 37% who travels from 6-15km; lastly, 12.50% of the

respondents travels from 16-30km from home to venue. This means that majority of the respondents just live near the training venue; while smaller portion of the respondents live far and travels farther from home to venue. This further imply that the training venue is easily accessible.

Table 1.4 presents the profile of respondents in terms of educational attainment. It can be gleaned in the table that majority (62.50%) of the respondents are master's degree holder; while the remaining 37% are with doctorate degree units. This means that the respondents are composed of highly educated and career focused individuals.

Table 1.5 presents the profile of respondents in terms of teaching experience. The table shows that majority (62.50%) of the respondents has 5-10 years teaching experience; while the remaining 37.50% have 11-15 years of teaching experience. This means that the respondents have already experienced trainings for professional development that help strengthen teaching related skills.

Table 1.6 presents the profile of respondents in terms of participated related trainings. It is revealed that majority of the respondents have participated district level related trainings; while the remaining 37.50% participated division level related trainings. This implies that this specific group of learning facilitators only attended lower-level trainings which suggest that they had fewer or limited chances of advance trainings. This is mostly because this specific group belong in the teaching force and not in managerial of instructional positions unlike school heads or master teachers; thus, they are not sent to advanced trainings.

Table 2.1 revealed that the respondents experience major problems in pre-training with grand mean 3.787, and with mean scores ranging from 3.500-4.375 in the following items: 1-Difficulty in preparing for the session content due to inadequate time(4.250); 2-Lack of support in preparation for the session in terms of resources: Load, internet connection, materials, etc. (3.875) ;3- Insufficient resources or materials for the sessions(3.500); 4- Difficulty balancing facilitation duties with other responsibilities due to busy schedule(4.375);6-lack of access to necessary resource materials such as books, research, handouts, etc.(4.000);7-Unclear expectations or roles regarding responsibilities as facilitators(3.625); 8- Dealing with own prejudices, anxiety, insecurity and stress as trainer(3.625);12- Multifaceted roles, functions and tasks as a learning facilitator;13- Access to technology, strong fast and reliable internet connection(3.500);15- Lack time knowing and studying about the needs, expectations etc. of participants(3.750);16- Setting SMART objectives in alignment to the participants needs and expectations(3.875);17- Crafting engaging activities that measure learning outcomes and satisfaction of the participants(3.750); 18- Choosing most appropriate methods, tools, and materials for the session. (3.875) ;19- Limited time to rehearse or run through session, practice delivery (4.250);20- test equipment, gadget of technology (4.250).

Most importantly, the learning facilitators experienced severe-problem in item number 5 or *Insufficient access to training or professional development for facilitation skills* with mean score- 4.625. Using the scale in the study, this means that the learning

facilitators experienced extremely problematic or has a significant and overwhelming impact; urgent attention or intervention is needed. Can affect a person's well-being, functioning, or the overall situation in a very negative way within 95-100%. The grand score 3.787 or Major problem in pretraining boils down to the critical gap in training and skill development of the learning facilitators. This further indicates that there is an abrupt or instant need for more professional development related training opportunities. Also, all these results suggests that the facilitators certainly need support in terms of time, resources and training opportunities related to their tasks.

There are outnumbering challenges connected with their roles these involved: a. Time limitations or time constraints and the need to avoid the image of experts (Margalef, and Robin, 2018); b. Difficulties with the decisions when to intervene and when to hold back in a learning process (Williams, 2012); c. Resource constraints/ Financial limitations (Piala, 2024); d. Limited guidance how to prepare facilitators (Freeman et al (2010)); e. Balancing work-based activities, personal engagement, institutional barriers and fostering community practices (Psych Educ, 2024); f. Professional development availability, cost and design as well as instructional supervision; g. Carrying out multiple roles (Johnston, 2016); h. Inconsistent practice, safety and accountability (Crozier et al, 2020); i. Barrier to technology implementation or technology is not utilized effectively (Kormos, 2021); and j. Teacher resistance (Lewis, 2026).

Table 2.2. shows During-training Extent of Problems Encountered by Learning Facilitators. It reflected that learning facilitators experience moderate problems during-training with grand mean of 3.344, with mean scores ranging from 3.500-3.875 in 3- Difficulty engaging participants during the session due to lack of interest or lack of motivation; 10- Unreliable internet connection during session; 14- Dealing with participants' resistance (reluctant to engage discussion) to the content process intimidating the session; 15- Managing personal stress or anxiety while facilitating; 17- Inadequate back-up or support for materials and resources; and 18- Lack of alternative plan in place for key facilitators being absent, sick or unavailable. Most importantly, the facilitators experience Severe problem in number 12- Inadequate space and ventilation of the venue or room set-up with mean score 4.500.

Aligning participants in a diverse group; Handling silence when people don't engage; and managing participation levels are among the common challenges of learning facilitators during training (Velasco, 2024). To counter this, delivering a program with more than one facilitator can be beneficial for both the learners and the facilitators. Two facilitators at a time can offer feedback and support (discprofiles.com, 2024).

The grand mean score 3.344 indicates that the learning facilitators experience moderate problems during sessions. These problems are noticeable and impactful but less intense than major or severe problems; may cause some level of inconvenience, discomfort, or disturbance, but doesn't pose a critical threat; may be manageable or require only moderate intervention within 85-89%. This suggests that the learning facilitators somehow experience less serious problems during training compared to pre-training. Also further suggest that the facilitators were able to solve and managed these

problems with the presence of the program and learning management team during training.

Table 2.3 shows Post-training Extent of Problems Encountered by Learning Facilitators. It reflected that learning facilitators experienced major problems in post training with grand mean score of 3.516, with mean scores ranging from 3.625-4.000. Specifically, with 1- Measuring how participant apply learnings from the sessions into application in the actual work setting (3.625); 2- Ensuring learning continuity (3.625); 4- Inadequate time and interest for debriefing after sessions (3.750); 7-Problems of follow-up or ensuring participants apply learning (3.750); 8- Stress and burnout from facilitating sessions (4.000).

The grand mean 3.516 indicated major problems experienced in post-training, with the highest mean score in statement number 8- Stress and burnout from facilitating sessions indicating that learning facilitators experienced stress and burned out after the sessions as serious issue that has a substantial impact but may not be as urgent or extreme as a "severe" problem, yet significant enough to cause distress or disruption and would require attention and solution but not immediately within 90-94%. Tarissa et al. (2023) said that teachers can use versatile strategies, especially emotion-focused coping strategies, to cope with stress. In addition, when it comes to teachers' well-being, it is important to find the most suitable coping strategies for one-self in different situations and also adding problem-focused coping strategies to one's coping repertoire should be acknowledged to possibly decrease teachers' stress and to ameliorate their sleep. This has practical implications for both preservice and in-service teacher training as places for learning these strategies.

Table 3.1 District's Extent of Compliance Level in Terms of Program Management. Table shows that the district is mostly compliant in program management with grand mean 4.4744. Indicating high level of compliance during the recently concluded in-service training of teachers. However, there are specific items with partial compliant such as 6- Training Venue has facilities for individuals with disabilities or special needs (e.g., ramps, signposts, toilets, reception, parking, elevator, etc.)(3.375); 8- Residential Accommodation is clean, well-lit, and well-ventilated(2.875); 9- Residential Accommodation is spacious for a maximum of three participants in a room with separate beds and at least one toilet and bathroom per room(2.625);17- There is a provision for fast and reliable internet access(3.000); and 22- Information on the venue's emergency evacuation plan is disseminated before the start of the activity(2.875).

Table 3.2 shows district's Extent of Compliance Level in Terms of Learning Management. The table reflected that the district is fully compliant with the grand score of 4.634. However, there are items with mostly compliant levels such as: 29- The resource speakers/ -subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by expressing ideas with clarity, logic, and correct grammar. (4.375); and 31- The resource speakers/ -subject matter expert demonstrate good communication skills (verbal and non-verbal) by using well-modulated voice in facilitating the session. (4.375).

Table 4 shows Correlation between profile of respondents and extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators in pre-training, during training and post training. The table presents no significant relationship to Sex, Age, Distance from home to venue, Highest Educational Attainment, Years of Teaching Experience, and Level of Participated Related Trainings. This implies that there is no statistically significant correlation between the pairs of variables because all p-values are greater than 0.05. Thus, in all cases, the decision is “accept null hypothesis” since there is insufficient evidence to suggest a significant relationship between the variables. This further suggest that there is insufficient evidence to conclude that these profile characteristics influence the training problems faced by learning facilitators.

Although there are some variables that show moderate or strong correlations: First, Age and the Extent of problems encountered during training (-0.660, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.075), which suggests older respondents might experience fewer problems during training, but it is still not statistically significant; Secondly, Years of training experience and extent of problems encountered during training problems (-0.524, Moderate Negative, p-value = 0.1820), which suggests that more experienced teachers might face fewer problems during training, but the result showed no statistical significance; Lastly, Distance from home to training venue and the extent of problems encountered in post-training (0.351, Weak Positive, p-value = 0.394), which suggests that those learning facilitators who live farther from the venue may experience more post-training problems, but the evidence is weak. All these cannot be confidently linked to training problems. To strengthen the analysis, there is a need for a larger sample size or population to further identify actual influences.

Table 5 shows the Correlation between learning facilitators’ extent of problems and district’s compliance level. The table presents no significant relationships between the extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators from pre-training, during-training and post-training and the district’s compliance level in terms of program and learning management. This implies that the learning facilitators extent of problems experienced in pre-training, during training or post-training do not significantly affect or correlate with the district’s compliance level in terms of program and learning management or vice versa. Or that these problems do not have statistically significant relationship with how well the district adheres and follows with the standards in program and learning management.

Although there are variables that suggest strong negative correlations: First, Extent of Post Training Problems and Compliance Level of Program Management (-0.683, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.062), which suggests that as post-training problems increase, compliance with program management decreases. However, the p-value is slightly above, meaning it is not statistically significant but borderline; Second, Extent of During Training problems & Compliance Level of Program Management (-0.607, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.111), which means that there is a potential strong negative relationship, but still not statistically significant. These strong negative correlations suggest trends, but these lack statistical significance which leads to the decision: fail to reject null; hypothesis. The closest significance is post-training problems and program

management compliance (p-value = 0.062) which suggest a possible relationship that might need a large sample size or further investigation. Also, these findings suggests that other factors aside from district's compliance level of program and learning management could actually play more crucial role in determining challenges experienced by the learning facilitators. These could include institutional policies, limited resources, or any external factors.

According to some related studies, there are outnumbering challenges connected with learning facilitators, these involved: a. Time limitations or time constraints and the need to avoid the image of experts (Margalef, and Robin, 2018); b. Difficulties with the decisions when to intervene and when to hold back in a learning process (Williams, 2012); c. Resource constraints/ Financial limitations (Piala, 2024); d. Limited guidance how to prepare facilitators (Freeman et al (2010); e. Balancing work-based activities, personal engagement, institutional barriers and fostering community practices (Psych Educ, 2024); f. Professional development availability, cost and design as well as instructional supervision; g. Carrying out multiple roles (Johnston, 2016); h. Inconsistent practice, safety and accountability (Crozier et al, 2020); i. Barrier to technology implementation or technology is not utilized effectively (Kormos, 2021); and j. Teacher resistance (Lewis, 2026). Lastly, according to Morales et al. (2023) there is a need to underscore teachers' involvement in graduate/post graduate studies. Certainly, if there will be more teachers who will be qualified to deliver sessions with CPD units then the burden of facilitation by the learning facilitators can be mitigated or can be lessened. DepEd order no. 44, s. 2023 entitled Interim Guidelines for the Quality Assurance and Monitoring and Evaluation of the National Educators Academy of the Philippines clearly emphasized the standard of qualifications for resource speakers or learning facilitators for the in-service program: (1.) Subject matter experts; (2.) Full-fledge Masters' Degree holder in the field of specialization; and (3.) Expert in professional development.

Table 6 presents the respondents' answers to the question "What Possible improvement in terms of In-service training can help you somehow lighten your load as a full-fledge learning facilitator in the district?" The answers given by the learning-facilitators are the following: (1) longer preparation, ample or enough time to prepare, (2) use the master-teachers as learning facilitators, (3) more trainings or capacity building, (4) increased number of full-fledge learning facilitator, (5) resources ready in pre-during-post training sessions, (6) assistant facilitators.

The most common themes that came out are the following:

1. Time- The learning facilitators emphasized the need of enough time to prepare for the sessions. From strategies, techniques, how to tailor fit the session to the needs of the participants, visual aids, sessions guides, slide decks, etc. there are so many things to do. Giving the learning facilitators time would really ease their tensions and stress in preparation of the sessions.
2. More Full-fledge LF or Master's Degree holders- Master teachers, instructional leaders, administrators or not, the learning facilitators recognized the great need

of the district to have an increased number of full-fledged learning facilitators in order to have more manpower who can deliver in-service sessions with CPD units.

3. Resources- Load allowance/data/internet, cartolina, adhesives, etc. must be readily available in the entire phases of the in-service program (pre, during and post training) to avoid cramming, stress, etc.
4. Training- The Learning facilitators highlighted their need for more trainings as they are not that exposed to facilitation unlike the master teachers.

The need for enough time in preparing the sessions, etc., assistant facilitator, trainings and capacity building as learning facilitators, resources and most especially more full-fledge colleagues because there are only 9 full-fledge learning facilitators in the district who are qualified to run sessions with Continuing professional Development units. All master teachers in the district are not full-fledge Master degree holders, and out of 181 total population of teachers, instructional leaders and administrators in the district, only 9 are full-fledge. There is an immense need indeed to to underscore teachers' involvement in graduate/post graduate studies (Morales, et al. 2023).

Additionally, the following were found as viable interventions and solutions for the challenges or problems encountered by the learning facilitators:

(a.) Research-based characteristics of professional development; (b.) Supportive administration and adequate funds for materials (Richardson, 2003); (c.) Collaboration and reflective practices (Psych Educ, 2024); (d.) Encouraging all teachers to involve in graduate/post-graduate studies(Morales et al, 2023); (e.) Training for facilitators' mental resilience and agility (Lago et al, 2019); (f.) Administrators must design more effective continued learning opportunities and focus on how to effectively integrate technology (Kormos, 2021); (g.) Focus on problem based learning; (h.) Creating approaches to enhance facilitator training and optimizing resources (Salinitri et al,); (i.) Time intensive form of professional development (Lewis, 2026); (j.) Facilitators learn to adapt to the needs of community by reflection and continuous feedback (Margalef et al, 2018); (k.) Collaborative learning on group development and dynamics (Williams, 2012); (l.) Encourage collegiality and make use of outside facilitator/staff or developer if necessary (Richarson, 2003); (m.) Leadership and targeted interventions (Piala et al, 2024); (n.) Fostering supportive environment (Bhati et al, 2009); (o.) Peer-learning and structuring the learning (Adriansen and Madsen, 2012); and (p.) Peer-learning and structuring the learning (Adriansen and Madsen, 2012); and (p.) Timely and constant training for learning facilitators.

Conclusions

The results of the study showed that (1). Majority of the respondents are 25-35 years old (75%) while 34-45 years old takes only 25% of the population; (2) Majority of the respondents are 25-35 years old (75%) while 34-45 years old takes only 25% of the population; (3) Majority or half (50%) of the respondents travels from 1-5km to reach the venue. This further followed by 37% who travels from 6-15km; lastly, 12.50% of the respondents travels from 16-30km from home to venue; (4) Majority (62.50%) of the

respondents are master's degree holder; while the remaining 37% are with doctorate degree units; (5) Majority (62.50%) of the respondents has 5-10 years teaching experience; while the remaining 37.50% have 11-15 years of teaching experience; (6) Majority of the respondents have participated district level related trainings; while the remaining 37.50% participated division level related trainings; (7) The respondents experienced major problems in pre-training with grand mean 3.787; (8) Learning facilitators experience moderate problems during-training with grand mean of 3.344; (9) Learning facilitators experienced major problems in post training with grand mean score of 3.516; (10) The district is mostly compliant in program management with grand mean 4.4744; (11.) The district is fully compliant with learning management with the grand score of 4.634; (12.) There is no significant relationship between Sex, Age, Distance from home to venue, Highest Educational Attainment, Years of Teaching Experience, Level of Participated Related Trainings and the extent of problems encountered by the respondents.

This further suggest that there is insufficient evidence to conclude that these profile characteristics influence the training problems faced by learning facilitators. (13.) There is no significant relationships between the extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators from pre-training, during-training and post-training and the district's compliance level in terms of program and learning management; (14.) In the question "What Possible improvement in terms of In-service training can help you somehow lighten your load as a full-fledge learning facilitator in the district?" The answers given by the learning-facilitators are the following: (1) longer preparation, ample or enough time to prepare, (2) use the master-teachers as learning facilitators, (3) more trainings or capacity building, (4) increased number of full-fledge learning facilitator, (5) resources ready in pre-during-post training sessions, (6) assistant facilitators. The most common themes that came out are more Time, Full-fledge Learning Facilitators or Master's Degree holders; Trainings and Resources.

The district's compliance level in terms of program management indicated a high level of compliance which is 4.4744. Considering the rating scale used in this study, this means that most requirements are met, with only minor deviations or occasional lapses within 90-94%. This indicates that the district was able to manage and to maintain a harmonious flow of the in-service training in spite of the existence of the facilitators' major problems in pre-training and post-training. This could also further indicate that the program management guidelines or standards may not be flexible enough and comprehensive enough to fully cater and grasp the needs of the learning facilitators, especially in pre-taring and post-training.

The district's compliance level in terms of learning management indicated a high level of compliance which is 4.634. Considering the rating scale used in this study, this means that all requirements are consistently met without any exceptions. (95-100%). This indicates that the districts' activities and practices pertaining to teaching-learning process were properly executed or properly made even if the facilitators experienced major problems in pre-training and post-training. This further means that the facilitators were very versatile and job oriented being the driver or manager of the entire teaching-learning

process. Well, this was made possible because the facilitators underwent several proof-reading, ran through discussions and multiple revisions of their session guides and slide decks with the administrators and instructional leaders, days before the actual in-service program of the district. This could also suggest that the problems encountered by the facilitators in pre-training and post-training have nothing to do with the learning management in other words, these problems could be actually outside or external to the learning management like issues with scarcity of resources, time constraints, etc. which are not the priority to be addressed by the learning management.

The extent of problems encountered by learning facilitators from pre-training, during training and post-training were fluctuating from major problem to moderate to major problem. This could mean that although the program management and learning management of the in-service training was with high compliance, it did not provide aid or help to learning facilitators in dealing with their existing problems which could include external factors such as scarcity of resources, time constraints, etc. This indicates that the districts' compliance of program and learning management is not really basically dealing about the facilitators' direct experiences but only and merely more about the adherence to teaching standards and practices.

This calls for the immediate attention of the big wigs of the Department of Education and the National Educators' Academy of the Philippines, if in-service training with CPD units will be continued and spontaneously pursued, then it would be nice to have robust or strong support systems not only for the program and learning management but also for the facilitators as well. There is a need to update the guidelines. As there seemed to be a disconnection between the training content and the facilitators' actual experiences and need in the training. It would be nice to have the needed alterations or changes in terms of support system, resources, training content, etc. to cater the needs of the facilitators. The varied responses of the respondents in terms of extent of problems encountered from pre-during-and post training indicates that the experiences of the learning facilitators were not identical or not the same. This could suggest that some facilitators might experience more serious problems than others, possibly due to individual circumstances or other external factors. On the contrary, lower standard deviations in district's compliance level in terms of program and learning management means that the district was consistent all throughout considering the guidelines and standards, though the facilitators were faced with problems all by themselves. Even if the study failed to reject all the hypothesis, there are several interesting discoveries that emerged in this study such as:

(1.) The learning facilitators encountered different extent of problems in pre-during and post-training, while the district's compliance level in terms of program and learning management appeared strong and consistent; (2.) There are some variables that show moderate or strong correlations but not statistically significant, these are: Age and the Extent of problems encountered during training (-0.660, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.075; Years of training experience and extent of problems encountered during training problems (-0.524, Moderate Negative, p-value = 0.1820); and Distance from home to training venue and the extent of problems encountered in post-training (0.351, Weak Positive, p-value =

0.394). All these cannot be confidently linked to training problems but analysis can be strengthened by increasing sample size or population to further identify actual influences; (3.) There are variables that suggest strong negative correlations but not statistically significant: Extent of Post Training Problems and Compliance Level of Program Management (-0.683, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.062); Second, Extent of During Training problems & Compliance Level of Program Management (-0.607, Strong Negative, p-value = 0.111). These strong negative correlations suggest trends but not statistically significant. The closest significance is post-training problems and program management compliance (p-value = 0.062) which suggest a possible relationship that might need a large sample size or further investigation.

(4.) Results of non-significance could as well show that there is disconnection or gap between the existing standards or guidelines for district compliance of program and learning management from NEAP from the actual training experiences of the facilitators; and lastly, variability or the differences in learning facilitators experiences in pre-during and post-training leads to the importance of understanding each unique individuality and circumstances of each facilitator including their ability to overcome challenges. There is a need to address the specific, persistent issues that learning facilitators encounter. Additionally, it must be noted that the number of respondents is typically small (8/9). In statistics, larger sample size is needed to improve accuracy, reliability, and generalizability of statistical findings. Thus, future researchers could also increase this sample size to further verify results of the study.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions the following are the recommendations:

1. Provide more professional development related training opportunities to Learning Facilitators. Also, the facilitators certainly need support in terms of time, resources and training opportunities related to their tasks.
2. Administrators must provide caliber support system to facilitators from pre-during-post training.
3. Encourage all teachers to pursue continuous professional development or pursue graduate and post graduate studies so that the number of full-fledge facilitators teachers will increase.
4. There is a need for robust or strong support systems not only for the program and learning management in in-service training but also for the facilitators as well. There is a need to update the guidelines. As there seemed to be a disconnection between the training content and the facilitators' actual experiences and need in the training. It would be nice to have the needed alterations or changes in terms of support system, resources, training content, etc. to cater the needs of the facilitators.
5. Future researchers could also make a parallel study and increase this sample size to further verify results.

6. The following were found as viable interventions and solutions for the challenges or problems encountered by the learning facilitators:
 - (a.) Research-based characteristics of professional development;
 - (b.) Supportive administration and adequate funds for materials (Richardson, 2003);
 - (c.) Collaboration and reflective practices (Psych Educ, 2024);
 - (d.) Encouraging all teachers to involve in graduate/post-graduate studies (Morales et al, 2023);
 - (e.) Training for facilitators' mental resilience and agility (Lago et al, 2019);
 - (f.) Administrators must design more effective continued learning opportunities and focus on how to effectively integrate technology (Kormos, 2021);
 - (g.) Focus on problem-based learning;
 - (h.) Creating approaches to enhance facilitator training and optimizing resources (Salinitri et al,);
 - (i.) Time intensive form of professional development (Lewis, 2026);
 - (j.) Facilitators learn to adapt to the needs of community by reflection and continuous feedback (Margalef et al, 2018);
 - (k.) Collaborative learning on group development and dynamics (Williams, 2012);
 - (l.) Encourage collegiality and make use of outside facilitator/staff or developer, if necessary (Richardson, 2003);
 - (m.) Leadership and targeted interventions (Piala et al, 2024);
 - (n.) Fostering supportive environment (Bhati et al, 2009);
 - (o.) Peer-learning and structuring the learning (Adriansen and Madsen, 2012);
 - (p.) Timely and constant training for learning facilitators.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that this study was done with serious consideration of ethical standards. Informed consent for the participants and permission letters for the gate keepers were accomplished religiously. All these aimed to give the participants a bird's eye view of all the research purpose, procedures, including their rights and benefit in participating with the study. Additionally, confidentiality and anonymity were maintained all throughout the study in order to protect the identity and well-being of the participants. Furthermore, the researchers declare that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of research. Lastly, proper citations of references were made to make sure of academic integrity.

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